

Semiconductor Package EMI Shield Using Metal Clip Attach

Frederick Ray I. Gomez

Central Engineering and Development NPI, Back-End Manufacturing & Technology, STMicroelectronics, Inc.
Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines 4027

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I. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

- Semiconductor packages may have input/output (I/O) signals that are sensitive and critical to electromagnetic interference (EMI), ultimately affecting and degrading the functionality of the signals

Fig. 1. Example of semiconductor package with EMI problem.

II. PACKAGE DESIGN SOLUTION

- The semiconductor package is augmented with metal clips through clip attach process to have EMI protection covering parts of the die, wirebonds, and metal traces
- Metal clips are connected to ground signal net of the semiconductor package to have EMI shielding on affected areas

Fig. 2. Improvement on EMI shielding performance.

- Package electrical modeling simulation results confirmed the improvement on EMI shielding performance of the package